

Preparation of Formaldehyde by the Dehydrogenation of Methyl Alcohol : A Study of Various Catalysts.

Part I.

By

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The technical processes for the preparation of formaldehyde are based on the fractional combustion of methyl alcohol, mostly with prepared copper as catalyst. The investigations of Sabatier and Mailhe (*Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1910, 344, 20), Orloff, (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 39, 855, 1023, 1414; 1908, 40, 7), Leblanc and Plasche (*Zeit. Elektrochem.*, 1911, 17, 45) have proved that the first stage of the reaction consists in the dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol according to the equation,

“Unfortunately, in the case of methyl alcohol, copper appears rapidly to lose its activity, either owing to the gradual reduction of unchanged cuprous oxide in solid solution in the metal, which may be the real effective catalytic agent, or for some other cause as yet unknown” (Rideal and Taylor, “Catalysis in Theory and Practice,” p. 128). But if the hydrogen is removed by combustion with air the catalytic activity of copper is maintained steady.

In this investigation, our aim has been to obtain a catalyst which will have a high and steady dehydrogenating capacity thus enabling formaldehyde to be prepared on a large scale by the dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol. The process has the advantage that hydrogen is obtained as a by-product, which has a high calorific value of 68,000 cal. per gram molecule, whereas the process of dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol is an endothermic one requiring only 12,000 cal. per gram molecule (approximately).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement will be clear from Fig. 1. Pure methyl alcohol was boiled in a flask, with a side tube, by immersion in a thermostat. In order to ensure steady and constant evaporation of alcohol, the level of alcohol in the flask was always kept constant. The vapours passed into a long reaction tube placed inside an electric furnace, with the catalytic material at the middle of the tube. The quantity of methyl alcohol passing over into the reaction tube was found to be 16 c.c., 21 c.c., and 28 c.c., per hour when the temperature of the evaporating bath was 68°, 68°·5, and 69° respectively. The furnace was maintained at a constant temperature by regulating the resistance. To prevent methyl alcohol condensing inside the tube, before entry into the furnace, the delivery tube was wound round with a manganin wire and maintained at about 100° by passing an electric current. The temperature was read off by means of a thermometer placed in contact with the catalytic material. The outflow gases were passed through two condensers as shown in the diagram and finally collected in a Hempel gas burette for analysis.

Fig. 1

Experimental Data with Copper Catalyst in Presence of various Promoters.

Catalyst No. 1.

A solution of Merck's pure copper acetate was precipitated with excess of caustic soda (Kahlbaum), the precipitate thoroughly washed with distilled water and then dried in an oven at 110°. Eighteen gm. of this material in the form of powder were packed between asbestos fibres and reduced at 180° in a slow current of pure hydrogen for 48 hours. The catalyst was kept in an atmosphere of hydrogen in the intervals between two experiments. The data with this catalyst are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I.

Volume of catalyst space = 9.8 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 18 gm. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	Temp of evaporation of MeOH or rate of evaporation of MeOH in c.c. per hour.	Total period of previous run at the time of collecting reaction products.	Space velocity-Vol. in c.c. of gas mixture of CO ₂ , CO, CH ₄ and H ₂ collected per c.c. of catalyst per hour.	ANALYSIS OF GAS.				Liquid mixture of MeOH and formaldehyde collected per hour in c.c.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
180°	70.5° or 60 c.c. per hour.	2 hrs.	943	3.1	7.8	2.2	86.6	...
"	"	3 hrs. 45 min.	637	5.0	3.8	3.8	87.0	...

After 5 hours' work the activity of the Catalyst No. 1 was found to diminish slowly but regularly. It was felt that the catalyst being in the form of powder was susceptible to "channelling" and the diminished activity might

be due to methyl alcohol vapour passing through some fixed pores whose walls might have lost their activity. Catalyst No. 2 was obtained in the form of pills in order that the effect of channelling, if any, might be eliminated.

Catalyst No. 2.

Copper oxide (5.5 g.) obtained from pure copper acetate was made into a large number of small pills when still in the moist state by the clean hand with the application of minimum pressure and reduced as before.*

TABLE II.

Volume of catalyst space = 2.6 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 5.5 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of MeOH introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	ANALYSIS OF GAS				Undecomposed MeOH collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
180°	50	30 min.	1039	1.8	3.1	2.7	92.0	27.6
"	37	2 hrs.	1016	3.6	2.7	4.1	89.0	11.25
190°	28	4 hrs. 40 min.	1431	2.0	5.4	3.4	89.1	8.0

* A pellet making machine could not be used, as the compressed pellets of CuO, after complete reduction, were found to have surprisingly small activity and even then the activity diminished rapidly. It is clear that catalysis being a surface reaction the essential condition for a good catalyst is a loose spongy structure which is not attained if pressure is used in making pellets. It may be mentioned here that if the oxide material when almost dry, is broken up into small bits and only those particles which passed through a 10-mesh sieve but not through a 20-mesh sieve, were used as catalyst after reduction, the results obtained are identical with catalyst made into small pills by hand.

This catalyst appeared very promising as it retained its activity undiminished for 6 hours, and experiments were continued with a fresh sample of a larger quantity of this catalyst (No. 3).

Catalyst No. 3.

Copper oxide (15.5 g.) obtained as before from copper acetate in the form of pills was packed in the reaction tube inside the furnace and reduced for twenty-four hours. Shrinkage was observed and the catalyst was re-packed and again reduced for 16 hours.

TABLE III.

Volume of catalyst space = 6 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 15.5 g. of oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection, after start.	Space velocity.	ANALYSIS OF GAS.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% OH ₄	% H ₂	
190°	28	50 min.	1040*	1.5	2.7	3.1	92.9	10
195°	"	3 hrs 20 min.	1170	2.2	6.9	3.3	87.4	6
"	"	12 hrs. 30 min.	1170	3.2	8.5	3.4	85.0	6
"	"	17 hrs.	900	3.1	7.2	3.5	86.0	7.5
"	"	21 hrs. 20 min.	660	3.0	7.8	3.2	85.8	8

The activity of this catalyst remained undiminished for 17 hours and thereafter it began to fall until at the 22nd hour the activity became about half of the initial value. The yield of formaldehyde per c.c. of catalyst

space per hour can be easily calculated. Now methyl alcohol and formaldehyde decompose thus :

The amount of formaldehyde left undecomposed therefore is equivalent to $(\text{H}_2 - 2\text{CO} - 2\text{CH}_4)$. The data marked with (*) in Table III therefore indicates that the yield of formaldehyde per hour per c.c. of catalyst

$$\begin{aligned} &= 1040 \times \frac{92.9 - 2 \times 2.7 - 2 \times 3.1}{100} \\ &= \frac{1040 \times 81.3}{100} = 846 \text{ c.c. gaseous formaldehyde.} \end{aligned}$$

The yield is satisfactory but unfortunately the catalyst was not very long-lived. Again, the quantity of liquid collected in the condensers which was mostly methyl alcohol, remaining undecomposed after passing over the catalyst, was not negligible. For successful industrial application, experimental conditions should be so chosen that the quantity of undecomposed methyl alcohol should become negligible. This can be achieved by raising the temperature of the catalyst, which, however, unfortunately has the effect of increasing considerably the decomposition of formaldehyde according to the equation $\text{HCHO} = \text{CO} + \text{H}_2$.

It was hoped that with the aid of promoters impregnating the copper catalyst, the desired end may be achieved. Before attempting to stabilise and enhance the activity of this catalyst by promoters, an investigation was made with various forms of copper catalyst in the pure state.

Catalyst No. 4.

Copper oxide (28.5 g.) obtained in the form of pills from copper sulphate by precipitation with caustic soda was taken.

TABLE IV.

Volume of catalyst space = 10.6 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 28.5 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C.c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	28	1 hour.	402	3.0	0.8	3.0	93.0	16
"	"	6 hours.	282	2.8	0.7	2.9	93.2	12

The initial activity of Catalyst No. 4 is $\frac{1}{4}$ of that of No. 3 and even this small activity rapidly diminishes till at the end of the 6th hour it has dropped to about $\frac{1}{5}$ th. The catalyst was discarded as unsuitable for investigation. No trace of sulphur could be detected chemically in this catalyst and the method of preparation was exactly the same as for Catalyst No. 3. It is strange that the catalytic activity of Catalyst No. 4 should be so entirely different from that of No. 3. In all future investigations, therefore, copper obtained from copper acetate was used as the catalyst base to which various promoters were added.

Catalyst No. 5.

Copper acetate (60 g.) and nickel acetate (0.3 g.) were dissolved together in a large quantity of water and precipitated with excess of caustic soda under constant stirring. This oxide (13.6 g.) made into small pills by the clean hand and reduced for 48 hours formed Catalyst No. 5.

TABLE V.

Volume of catalyst space = 6.9 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 13.6 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C.c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	28	4 hours	1218	2.8	10.5	2.8	84.0	3
"	"	10 hours.	1113	3.0	9.2	2.8	84.5	8.5
"	"	10 hrs. 45 mins.	860	2.9	9.6	3.1	84.2	15

The Catalyst No. 5 (100 g. copper acetate : 0.5 g. nickel acetate) at first proved successful, for the space velocity was 1218, and the undecomposed methyl alcohol per hour about 4 c.c. as against space velocity, 1170 and liquid collection of 6 c.c. per hour in the case of Catalyst No. 3, which did not contain any promoter. But this activity is short-lived, falling to $\frac{2}{3}$ of its initial value in 11 hours. The quality of this catalyst did not improve by increasing the nickel content (100 g. copper acetate : 1 g. nickel acetate), as the percentage of CO in the issuing gases rose from 10.8 to 13.6 indicating a larger

percentage decomposition of formaldehyde. The space velocity did not increase nor was the activity of the catalyst of longer duration.

Catalyst No. 6.

For this set of catalysts silver was used as promoter but the results were disappointing. This is rather surprising as the investigations of Bouliard (F. P. 412501/1910), Blank (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1911, 30, 49) and Hochstetter (B. P. 464/1914) have shown that silver is the best catalyst for the manufacture of formaldehyde by the fractional combustion of methyl alcohol. It appears that silver is effective as a dehydrogenating catalyst only when its surface is maintained in an active state by the combustion of hydrogen with oxygen of air to form steam. Silver acetate (0.07 g.) and copper acetate (70 g.) were dissolved together and the oxide was precipitated with caustic soda, sieved when almost dry between 10 and 20 meshes and reduced for 48 hours.

TABLE VI.

Catalyst No. 6 (a). (CuAc : AgAc :: 100 : 0.1).

Volume of catalyst space = 8.2 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 16 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C.c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
190°	28	1 hour.	600	4.4	3.0	2.6	90.0	9
"	"	9 hours.	454	4.7	4.5	3.0	87.6	7

Catalyst No. 6 (b). (CuAc : AgAc :: 100 : 0.5).

Volume of catalyst space = 7.4 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 15.8 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C.c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	28	1 hour.	773	2.9	9.6	2.7	84.8	4.6
"	"	7 hours.	584	3.2	12.0	3.6	80.6	16.6

Catalyst No. 6 (c). (CuAc : AgAc :: 100 : 5).

Volume of catalyst space = 7 c.c.

Weight of catalyst = 16.3 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C.c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	28	1 hour.	275	1.7	12.2	2.6	83.2	13;

It will be observed that the efficiency of the Catalyst No. 6 (a) is about half of that of pure copper catalyst. The stability is also less. With increasing quantity of silver as promoter, the catalyst became worse for our purpose in that the percentage of CO in the outflow gases correspondingly increased.

Catalyst No. 7.

In this set of catalysts, thorium oxide was used as promoter. Catalyst No. 7 (a) consisted of the reduced material from 16 g. of the oxide sieved between 10 and 20 meshes, obtained from a mixture of copper acetate and thorium nitrate in the ratio of 100 to 1. Catalyst No. 7 (b) being the same as above but the ratio of copper acetate to thorium nitrate was as 100 : 0.2. Catalyst No. 7 (c) consisted of the reduced material obtained from 32 g. of oxide, the ratio of copper acetate to thorium nitrate being 100 : 0.1.

TABLE VII.

Catalyst No. 7 (a).

Volume of catalyst space = 11.7 c. c.

Weight of catalyst = 16 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	21	10 hrs.	1169	1.9	15.4	3.4	79.2	2.5
180°	"	37	964	3.1	17.5	3.8	75.3	3
"	"	54	985	3.2	12.2	3.5	80.5	2

Catalyst No. 7 (b).

Volume of catalyst space = 10 c. c.

Weight of catalyst = 16 g. as oxide.

Temp of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	21	8 hrs.	1584	2.4	6.4	2.4	89.0	5
"	"	17	1560	2.1	3.6	3.3	91.0	4
205°	"	35	1584	1.8	6.0	4.0	87.8	3
215°	16	50	1536	2.6	13.2	5.2	78.5	1

Catalyst No. 7(c).

Volume of catalyst space=18.6 c.c.

Weight of catalyst=16 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	28	26 hrs.	967	2.0	5.5	3.1	89.0	8
205°	"	32	1224	2.4	4.8	2.8	90.0	4
"	21	35	900	2.4	4.5	2.5	90.0	1.2

A few of the typical data with thoria as promoter are given in Table VII. The following conclusions are at once reached: (1) The catalysts retained their activity unimpaired for an almost indefinite time. (2) When approximately the same amount of catalyst material is used, the activity of Catalyst No. 7(a) (1% thorium nitrate) is about the same as that of pure copper catalyst but that of No. 7(b) (0.2% thorium nitrate) is 1.5 times greater. (3) With increasing quantity of thorium nitrate,

decomposition of formaldehyde into CO and H₂ increases considerably and the suitability of the catalyst for the large scale production of formaldehyde correspondingly diminishes. (4) With increase in temperature, the quantity of undecomposed methyl alcohol diminishes but the percentage decomposition of formaldehyde into CO and H₂ increases. (5) Catalyst No. 7(c) (0.1% thorium nitrate) was obtained from 32 g. of the oxide material as against 16 g. in No. 7(b) and gave 18 litres of outflow gases per hour as against 15 litres from Catalyst No. 7(b). The space velocity was of course less but the total yield was greater. The quantity of undecomposed methyl alcohol was only 1.2 c.c. per hour when the furnace temperature was 205° and evaporating temperature 68°·5. The calculated yield of formaldehyde per hour was

$$= \frac{18,000 \times [90 - 2(4.5 + 2.8)]}{100}$$

=13,000 c.c. or approximately 15 g., the quantity of methyl alcohol introduced being $21 \times 0.8 = 16.8$ gm.

It thus appears that the problem of a suitable catalyst for the continued dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol to yield formaldehyde is solved by using thoria as promoter to the extent 0.1 g. thorium nitrate in 100 g. of copper acetate.

Catalyst No. 8.

The success of thoria as promoter naturally suggested the use of ceria, and the results obtained were even more satisfactory. Cerous nitrate (0.7 g., Kahlbaum) and copper acetate (70 g.) were precipitated together with pure caustic soda and the catalyst prepared in the usual way. This constituted Catalyst No. 8(a). In Catalyst

No. 8(b) the ratio of copper acetate to cerous nitrate was as 100 : 0.2 and in catalyst No. 8(c) the ratio was 100 : 0.1. The experimental data are given in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII.

Catalyst No. 8(a).

Volume of catalyst space=11.3 c.c.

Weight of catalyst=16 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start (in hours).	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	21	7	1816	1.9	21.7	3.7	72.5	3
190°	16	17	1594	2.7	16.1	3.6	77.6	2.7
180°	"	25	1275	1.8	12.5	4.7	80.8	2.5
"	"	36	1275	1.8	11.8	5.0	81.3	2.5

Catalyst No. 8(b).

Volume of catalyst space=9.6 c.c.

Weight of catalyst=16 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				% CO ₂	% CO	% CH ₄	% H ₂	
195°	21	15 hrs.	1550	2.0	3.9	4.7	88.9	3.5
"	16	24	1275	2.0	3.8	4.6	89.5	2
"	"	45	1300	2.8	4.8	3.5	88.4	1.5
200	"	56	1375	2.6	5.2	3.1	88.9	1.5

Catalyst No. 8(c).

Volume of catalyst space=8.8 c.c.

Weight of catalyst=16 g. as oxide.

Temp. of furnace.	C. c. of methyl alcohol introduced per hour.	Time of collection after start.	Space velocity.	Analysis of gas.				Undecomposed methyl alcohol collected per hour.
				%	%	%	%	
				CO ₂	CO	CH ₄	H ₂	
195°	16	12 hrs.	1637	3.7	5.1	3.7	87.5	2
"	"	25	1637	3.3	2.6	3.7	90.0	2.5
200°	"	32	1774	3.2	4.5	3.8	88.5	2
"	"	36	1774	3.2	5.0	2.8	89.0	1.5

It will be noticed that for all these catalysts the space velocity increased with increase in furnace temperature; in the case of Catalyst No. 8 (a), an increase in temperature from 180° to 195° increased the subsidiary decomposition of formaldehyde considerably, the CO percentage in the outflow gases rising from 12 to 22 per cent. approximately. For catalyst with lower ceria content, this subsidiary decomposition is much smaller and is not very sensitive to small changes in temperature. It will also be observed that under similar experimental conditions, the efficiency of the Catalyst No. 8 (c) is at least 25 per cent. greater than that of Catalyst No. 8 (b) with double ceria content. The rate of formation of formaldehyde per hour by Catalyst No. 8 (c) at 200°, when the evaporating bath for methyl alcohol is at 68°, is

$$= \frac{8.8 \times 1774 (89 - 16)}{100} \text{ or } 11,000 \text{ c.c. approxly.}$$

or 12.5 gm., the quantity of methyl alcohol introduced being 12.8 gm. The conversion is therefore almost quantitative. This catalyst is more efficient than Catalyst No. 7 (c) (with 0.1 per cent. thorium nitrate) as with half the catalyst material almost similar quantity of formaldehyde is produced.

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